

The Complementary Minds: A Logical Framework for Belief Formation

D. O. Anastassova, M. Badino, F. A. D'Asaro^{*,†}

Ethos Center, Department of Human Sciences,
University of Verona

Since the mid-1970s [Wason and Evans, 1974], approaches based on the duality of the mind have become commonplace in the cognitive sciences. They have been particularly successful in explaining phenomena as diverse as higher cognition, stereotypes, and decision-making [Frankish, 2010]. Famously, the driving idea is that our mind consists of two kinds of processes that are fundamentally different and that can be described by a number of traits. For example, several authors affirmed that while one process is fast, associative, bias-responsive, parallel, unconscious, effortless, and resource-saving, the other is slow, rule-based, norm-responsive, sequential, conscious, effortful, and resource-consuming [Kahneman et al., 2002, Evans and Frankish, 2009, Kahneman, 2011, Sloman, 2014]. Furthermore, it has been suggested that these processes are grounded in two different systems, i.e., specific brain areas, which support them separately [Evans, 2010].

[Evans and Stanovich, 2013] have called for a simplification of the terminology of dual-process theories. They dispensed with the systems language altogether and claimed that one should be committed only to the existence of two types of processes, namely, Type 1 (*T1* for short) and Type 2 (*T2* for short). More importantly, they distinguish between defining features and simple correlates. The *T1* process is defined by the fact that it is autonomous, while the *T2* process is defined by the fact that it uses working memory and is able to perform cognitive decoupling, i.e., to “create temporary models of the world and test out actions (or alternative causes) in that simulated world” [Stanovich, 2011].

T1 and *T2* processes are compatible with two architectures of the mind. The so-called “parallel-competitive” architectures assume that *T1* and *T2* processes are activated in parallel and compete to have their say in the resulting behavior [Sloman, 1996, Sloman, 2014]. Occasionally, this competition can wind up creating a conflict between the two processes. According to the “default-interventionist” architectures, a *T1* process first produces a default response, which, if necessary, can be subsequently checked by a *T2* process

*Corresponding author: fabioaurelio.dasaro@univr.it

†Authors are listed alphabetically.

[Kahneman et al., 2002, Kahneman, 2011, Evans and Stanovich, 2013]. These architectures avoid the conflict problem but must specify the conditions under which the reflective check is activated.

In this paper, we set up the task of developing the idea of a default-interventionist architecture. We concentrate on the case of producing a belief as the response to exposure to external evidence. Further, we assume that (1) the T1 process produces fast, default-like responses to external evidence and that (2) the T2 process might step in to check the response, but it always operates under limited resources. Given these assumptions, we ask: What is the appropriate logical framework to represent the default-interventionist architecture of belief formation? We argue that natural candidates to address this question are Depth-Bounded Boolean Logics (*DBBLs* for short), which have been developed in a series of works [D'Agostino, 2015, D'Asaro et al., 2021]. These logics, however, provide a hierarchy of tractable approximations of classical logic in which judgement about a proposition of interest is suspended whenever the agent is unable to derive its truth (or falsity). These logics model belief formation as a process that involves considering a proposition and then performing cognitive decoupling (as defined above) to explore all possible scenarios in favor of and against it. If the agent has sufficient cognitive resources to deliberate on the proposition, it may accept or reject it. Otherwise, its judgement will remain suspended. However, in order to account for the non-monotonic nature of belief formation, a modification of these logics is necessary that incorporates the possibility of initially accepting (or rejecting) information by default and later revising or rejecting it. Ongoing work by some of the authors aims to provide non-monotonic approximations of classical logic that can model cases where agents have a bias towards a belief due to insufficient cognitive or computational resources. These developments will hopefully provide a unified framework in which a unified account of the dual-process belief formation can be naturally expressed. Future steps in this direction will involve experimental and theoretical work to validate the logical framework, study its scope and applicability to real agents, and possibly expand it to deal with further phenomena observed in practical reasoning.

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